

Personal exposure to black carbon and its deposition on human lungs in different micro-environments; during commuting and in the office

A. Khan¹, L. Davulienė¹, S. Šemčuk¹, K. Kandrotaitė^{1,2}, A. Minderytė¹, M. Davtalab¹, I. Uogintė¹, M. Skapas¹, V. Dudoitis¹, and S. Byčėnienė¹

¹SRI Centre for Physical sciences and technology, Saulėtekio Ave. 3, Vilnius, Lithuania

²Faculty of Physics, Vilnius University, Universiteto str. 3, LT-01513 Vilnius, Lithuania

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Presenting author email: abdullah.khan@ftmc.lt

Black carbon (BC) mass concentration values for urban areas are not available from standard air quality monitoring networks in many countries because BC is not currently regulated by the EU Air Quality Directive and WHO (Brewer, 2019).

The urban micro-environments are very complex due to the different emission sources and their intensity; therefore, a combination of mobile and stationary measurements allows for a better understanding of the dynamics of BC, whose spatial variation is larger than that of PM_{2.5}—the EU air quality standard. In this study, real-time measurements of BC mass concentrations were performed in an office and on a daily commute to assess work-related personal exposure to BC deposition in the lungs of a participant. The study was conducted in Vilnius, Lithuania, in the spring of 2022. The hourly mean BC mass concentration in March 2022 at the urban background station ranged from 0.30 to 9.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with traffic-related BC (BC_{tr}) accounting for 66% of the total BC mass concentration. The highest BC mass concentrations were observed during peak hours, reaching up to 7.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at hotspots (Figure 1).

The results of the multi-path particle dosimetry model show that the minute deposition dose of BC (MDD_{BC}) during the working day (including during commuting and office hours) was the highest in the morning rush hour at 52 ng/min and in the evening at 26 ng/min, demonstrating the influence of traffic exhaust emissions on aerosol particles, especially on fine particles. Significant differences were found between the MDD_{BC} in the office and a vehicle cabin. The MDD_{BC} value in the office was 0.005 $\mu\text{g}/\text{min}$, which was almost six times lower than the deposition dose for car drivers during the morning rush hour (Figure 2). The distribution of the MDD_{BC} in the human respiratory tract had a maximum in the pulmonary region ranging from 5.1 ng/min in the office to 19.9 ng/min in the car during the morning drive (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Source apportionment and time series of total particle number (N_{total}) and mass concentrations (M_{total}) of 10–430 nm aerosol particles from SMPS measurements at the urban background site in March 2022.

Figure 2. (A) measured BC time series inside and outside the vehicle, (B) BC concentration along the route; (C) respiratory deposition dose, and (D) statistics of BC concentration calculated from hourly averages.

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